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The Expected Prospects of Home Grown School Feeding Programme of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGS) through Primary Education in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges

Aernyi, I. , Ivagher, E. D. & Akura, G.G

ABSTRACT

The Nigerian Home Grown School Feeding (HGSF) program termed the National home grown school meal program (NHSMP) responds directly to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) related to hunger and poverty (MDG 1), education (MDG 2) and gender equality (MDG 3), and indirectly to child mortality and maternal health (MDGs 4 and 5). the aims to deliver a government-led, cost-effective school feeding programme using food that is locally grown by smallholder farmers. Children benefit from a hot nutritionally balanced school meal which reduce hunger and improve education outcomes; farmers benefit from improved access to school feeding markets and communities benefit from new catering, processing and food handling jobs. It brings a multiplier effect that will spur economic activities. With the vision of a sustainable school feeding programme that will establish a safety net for the poor and eradicate malnutrition in school age children while stimulating the national economy and a provision of a free meal a day to pupils in public primary schools in Nigeria by working constructively with stakeholders to ensure a sustainable implementation of the programme. This paper looks at the historical background of the programme, the expected prospects of the home grown school feeding, the paper considered issues and challenges of home grown school feeding, the paper made a conclusion and drew recommendations among others that, government should ensure that there is proper and explicit criterion for targeting school feeding programs that is regular all public primary schools. They should also provide funds for the feeding programmes in good time and ensure it is adequate for the schools according to the pupils' population.

Keywords: School Feeding, Millennium Development Goals.

INTRODUCTION

Historical Background

The history of home grown feeding can be traced from National School Lunch Program (NSLP) Act, in America signed by President Truman in 1946. By 1966 Child Nutrition Act expanded the program and added the School Breakfast Program (SBP) on a pilot basis; 1975 legislation made the SBP permanent; and 1998 legislation expanded the NSLP to include reimbursements for snacks served to students. (Isa, Ahmed and Khalid, 2012). Also, India is said to have a long tradition of school feeding program largely by the state governments with some external assistance (Akanbi and Alayande, 2011). India Supreme Court directed the state governments to introduce school feeding program in all government and government assisted primary schools. This was the result of a petition from the People's Union for Liberties, a large coalition of organizations and individuals that led to the Right to Food Campaign (Akanbi and Alayande, 2011). In Brazil, the school feeding program is in the country's national

constitution, and is part of the government's Zero Hunger Program. Covering nearly 37 million children each year, the program is among the largest in the world (Isa, Ahmed and Khalid, 2012). Its implementations are managed by an independent institution, the National Fund for Development of Education (FNDE), created in 1997, to be responsible for the disbursement of the financial resources for school meals in each municipality (Akanbi and Alayande, 2011). In the realization of the central role of nutrition to education, the Federal Government of Nigeria in collaboration with New Partnership for African Development (NEPAD), World Food Program (WFP), United Nations International Children's Fund (UNICEF), and other International Development Partners (IDPs), developed the Home Grown School Feeding and Health Program (HGSFHP).

Introduction

In order to improve the nutritional status of school children, the Federal Government of Nigeria launched the Home-Grown School Feeding and Health Programme in September, 2005 under the coordination of the Federal Ministry of Education. The programme aimed to provide pupils with adequate meal during the school day (FME, 2007). The scheme, officially known as Home Grown School Feeding Programme insisted on buying the foodstuffs from the local farmers. It therefore reduced the rate of malnutrition while it also provided the local farmers the opportunity to sell their produce to participating schools. According to the Federal Government's directive, Federal, State and Local Governments were to fund the programme with the State and Local Governments providing the bulk.

Upon the assumption into office of his excellency President Mohammed Buhari on the 29th of May 2016. His excellency has shown commitment to key campaign promises. One of these programs is the school feeding program which is a component of the National Social Investment Programme. The programme is chaired by the Vice-President which has been tasked with the responsibility to run with the program. A collaboration with Partnership for Child Development (PCD) was consummated with a memorandum of understanding (MOU) to offer technical assistance. PCD is internationally known for its success in various countries on child nutrition and school feeding. To rollout the program based on around a strategic structure, A core team was put together to drive the coordination of the program in collaboration with PCD and various key stakeholder ministries. The strategic make-up of the core team are Program Manager, Operations Manager, Funds Manager and a Monitoring and Evaluation Manager. This quickly evolved to A National team which comprises of officers from the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Health, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Budget and planning, Ministry of Justice with all the Social Investment Programmes under the office of the Vice- President, the school feeding programme funds are domiciled under the Ministry of Budget and Planning.

Expected Prospects of the Programme

School feeding programmes constitute critical interventions that have been introduced in many developed and developing countries of the world to address the issue of poverty, stimulate school enrolment and enhance pupils' performance. Akanbi, (2013). Observed that in developing countries, almost 60million children go to school hungry every day and about 40 percent of them are from Africa. Providing school meals is therefore vital in nourishing children. Parents are motivated to send their children to school instead of keeping them at home to work or care for siblings. The introduction of the school feeding is traced to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) initiative and several conferences held thereafter by African leaders which aimed to tackle issues, such as peace, security, good economic, political and corporate governance and to make the continent an attractive destination for foreign investment (Olusanya, 2010).

In Nigeria, These are the expected prospects of HGSFHP from the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs)

MDG	EXPECTED PROSPECTS OF HGSFHP
Eradicate extreme poverty and hunger	Reduction of child hunger Poverty reduction in communities
Achieve universal primary education	Increase in School Enrolment, Attendance, Retention, Completion and Achievement
Promote gender equality and empower women	Correct gender imbalance through increased girl-child enrolment in schools
Reduce child mortality	Improved nutritional and health status of learners
Improve maternal health	Improved income generation, nutrition and health education
Combat HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases	Improved nutritional and health status of Orphans and Vulnerable Children.

Source: National Guidelines for School Meal Planning and Implementation. (FME, 2007)

Eradication of extreme poverty and hunger

The idea of home grown feeding program will create a synergy between direct action against hunger and measures to stimulate and improve agriculture and the rural sector development. By this, the program aims to stimulate local agricultural production and boost the income of farmers by creating a viable and ready market via the school feeding programme. Children from poor family background could have better access to adequate food while in schools as a precondition of their participation in education. At the same time, increases in agricultural productivity and production will increase rural economic activity and expand employment opportunities in the farm and rural non-farm sector.

Achieve universal primary education

To achieve universal primary education, the Federal Government came up with the Universal Basic Education Act in 2004, which provided the enabling legislative backing for the execution of the Home Grown School Feeding and Health Programme. Towards the realization of the objectives of the Universal Basic Education programme and the central role of nutrition, the Federal Ministry of Education launched the Home Grown School Feeding and Health Programme in 2005. The overall goal of the program in Nigeria is to reduce hunger and malnutrition among school children and enhance the achievement of Universal Basic Education. The primary objectives of the program are to: Reduce hunger among Nigerian School Children; Improve the nutritional health status of school children; Increase school enrolment, attendance, retention and completion particularly of children in rural communities and poor urban neighbourhoods; and Enhance comprehension and learning achievements of pupils. All the above objectives are a drive towards achieving the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).

School Feeding Program Promotes gender equality and empower women

Education increases the probability of a girl playing an active role in her national social, political and economic activities. Poverty and tradition are the main reasons why the exclusion of girls from schooling is persistent and widespread. More than half of the 72 million¹ primary school-aged children not attending school are girls. Two-thirds of them are in poor communities of sub-Saharan Africa and South and East Asia.² Girls still drop out of school at higher rates than boys. School feeding, especially take-home rations increases the probability of parents sending their girls to school and keeping them there. Food can also support girls and women to receive literacy and numeracy training and vocational and life skills, even if they are not able to gain a formal education. These skills are empowering and critical for dealing with life decisions, caring for families, accessing jobs and other opportunities, and contributing to society. (Akanbi, and Alayande, 2011).

It is through education that the daughter of a peasant can become a doctor, that a son of a mineworker can become the head of the mine, that a child of farm workers can become the president of a great nation. (Nelson Mandela, 1995). School feeding helps close the gender gap in schools and helps to empower women by increasing their probability of employment. When girls are educated they are more likely to have fewer and healthier children and to head families that are food-secure. Maternal and infant mortality rates will decrease and better- educated girls will make more informed choices.

Reduce child mortality

School feeding contributes to educational impacts on future parents which in turn impacts the next generation. Education influences girls' economic opportunities, their participation in community, decision-making, HIV infections rates and the level of literacy and child malnutrition. School feeding encourages girls to stay in school thereby delaying early marriages and pregnancies. Girls who go to school marry later and have 50 per cent fewer children on average.

Improve maternal health and Combat HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases

School feeding contributes to improve maternal health and Combat HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases through its educational impacts on future parents and in turn impacts the next generation. Education influences girls' economic opportunities, their participation in community, decision-making, HIV infections rates and the level of literacy and child malnutrition. School feeding encourages girls to stay in school thereby delaying early marriages and pregnancies. Girls who go to school marry later and have 50 per cent fewer children on average. More mature and more educated mothers are usually better equipped to foster their children. Educated mothers start prenatal care early, are more likely to meet their own nutritional requirements when they are pregnant.

Issues and Challenges of the Home Grown School Feeding (HGSF) program

This section highlights some of the issues and challenges affecting the implementation of home-grown school feeding programme, based on existing empirical literature.

Geographical Targeting of Benefiting Schools

Geography is identified as the explicit criterion for targeting school feeding programs. A poverty and food security map, whether crude or sophisticated, informs decisions about the locations where school feeding programs operate. Sometimes, in addition to the geographic location, school characteristics that correlate with poverty are used. For example, preference might be given to schools with multi-grade classrooms where these tend to serve the poorest; conversely, private schools might be excluded because they are perceived to be a preserve for the richest. Where school feeding programs are relatively small, geographic targeting can be powerful and can result in most of the benefits going to the poor. A program that serves 10 percent of schools and is placed only in the poorest districts would have few errors of inclusion. But as coverage increases and grows towards universal, school feeding programs will include higher proportions of non-poor children (Bundy; Burbano; Grosh; Gelli;Jukes, and Drake 2009). In addition, urban areas are sometimes overlooked when poverty and food insecurity are assessed geographically because the lowest level of geographical targeting is often the district level. This can result in rural areas being identified as generally worse off, even though increased urbanization and the rapid growth of slum areas in cities have led to urban areas with large populations living in extreme poverty Once target areas have been identified, the next stage in the process involves school level targeting. In this process, selecting some schools and not others in a particular area might attract pupils from neighbouring schools, which are not receiving food, to those 31 that are targeted under the program (Bundy, et al; 2009).

School Feeding Modalities

There are real differences between the benefits of in-school feeding (meals) and take-home rations. The choice of school feeding modality, therefore, depends on program objectives. Similarly, there are significant differences in the appropriateness of the different modalities to local capacity and contexts. For in-school meals, the timing and composition of school meals depends on such local factors as the length of the school day, the nutritional status of children, local eating habits, availability of commodities (for example, in the case of in-kind donations), ease of preparation, shelf life of different commodities, and costs, as well as the availability of trained cooks, cooking facilities, and clean water (Bundy, et al; 2009). Cooking food in school involves the complications and costs of providing labour, fuel, and cooking and eating facilities. These

complications are reduced by the fact that they draw parental and community involvement into the program and may include food that is available locally, which is a key element of quality and sustainability 32

Costs of School Feeding Programmes

This is another challenge, the costs of school feeding programmes will depend on several different factors, including the choice of modality, the composition and size of the rations, whether the food is purchased locally or is imported, and the number of beneficiaries and school feeding days per year. Logistics, security, and climatic conditions have an impact on program expenditures. The geographical context will also affect the overall cost; programmes in landlocked countries will generally face greater operational costs than countries implementing the same type of program but have access to seaports, depending on the provenance of the food. Estimating the full cost of in-school meal programmes is not always straightforward because providing cooked meals in schools generally includes a range of school-level costs that are normally not included within overall program expenditures. The World Food Programme estimated that the costs (standardized over 200 days and 700-kcal) of providing a child with food at school were on average US\$34 per child per year in 2001 (World Food Programme, 2005) The choice of program objectives will to a large degree dictate the food modality (biscuits, cooked meals, or take-home rations) and associated implementation costs. Fortified biscuits can provide substantial nutritional inputs at a fraction of the cost of school meals, making them an appealing option for service delivery in food-insecure contexts. Both costs and effects should be considered carefully when designing the appropriate school-based intervention.

Community Involvement in Management of HGSF Programs

It is important to find the right balance between programs that count on community participation and ownership (which is a very positive factor in sustainability) and programs that seek to be largely funded by communities. There is a tendency to consider community-sustained programs as an option in reducing dependence on external assistance, but this places significant expectations on communities which they may not be able to fulfil. Indeed, there is anecdotal evidence from many low-income countries that communities introduce fees or in-kind contributions to support such programs, and by so doing erect barriers to education, particularly for girls and the poor citizenry. Additionally, this type of program by definition can only be sustained in food-secure and generally better-off areas in a country and cannot serve the populations that are most needy. Similarly, this model is particularly susceptible to shocks (for example, rising food prices or drought) and may have problems regarding the type, quality, and regularity of meals provided. Communities are expected to provide firewood, employ a cook, provide kitchen utensils, cooking water and monitor the utilization of the project's funds, as part of their contribution (MOE, 2009). 34

Accountability and Monitoring of Procurement Procedures

Any program that involve substantial quantities of commodities and longterm contracts, there are opportunities for corrupt practices in procurement and contracting associated with school feeding programs. While it is usually recognized that procurement from outside the country requires systematic tendering and bidding processes, there may be less awareness that these are also necessary and appropriate for competitive procurement, even down to the district level (Bundy, Burbano, Grosh, Gelli, Jukes, and Drake, 2009). This approach has proven effective in school-based management of budgets, provided that both inflows and expenditures are transparently shared within the beneficiary community. Procurement contracts for such components as transport, storage, and food preparation constitute another area where close monitoring and oversight are required, linked with strong tendering processes and transparency (World Food Programme, 2009)

CONCLUSION

The Home Grown School Feeding Programme (HGSFP) of the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN), a component part of its Social Investment Plans (SIPs) to tackle poverty and improve the health and education of children, it is also a response directly to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) related to hunger and poverty (MDG 1), education (MDG 2) and gender equality (MDG 3), and indirectly to child mortality and maternal health (MDGs 4 and 5). The aim is to deliver a government-led, cost-effective school feeding programme using food that is locally grown by smallholder farmers.is a commendable idea that must be encouraged by all. In the design of the programme, the FGN is to fund the feeding of pupils in Primary one to Primary three while the state governments are expected to fund pupils in Primary four to Primary six. The programme attracted N500 billion allocation in both the 2016 and 2017 budgets at the federal level and so far

the FGN has spent N6.2 billion during the academic year that ended in August. Although the programme has a target of three million, since its inception in 2016, it has made significant strides feeding 2, 827, 501 school children across 14 states of the federation. The states are Abia, Anambra, Bauchi, Benue, Delta, Ebonyi, Enugu, Kaduna, Ogun, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Taraba, and Zamfara states.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- (i) The government should ensure that there is proper and explicit criterion for targeting school feeding programs that is regular all public primary schools. They should also provide funds for the feeding programmes in good time and ensure it is adequate for the schools according to the pupils' population.
- (ii) There should be a manual to define the program objectives, the different roles of stakeholders and that standardizes processes for each programme so as to improve on the modalities of the program. This will prevent the loss of information that is being experienced across the programmes and leaders should educate parents on the importance of sending their children to school, whether there is feeding programme or not.
- (iii) The school management committee should support the feeding programme in schools by starting income-generating activities to raise funds to supplement the funds issued by the government towards the school feeding programme. Like engaging donors to assist in funding the programs is key to tackling the issue of operational costs. International donors with similar goals should be sought after to assist in the area of funding
- (iv) The community and parents should support feeding programmes in the school by helping to pay the cooks, providing fuel (firewood), giving their children feeding utensils and providing water, and accept it as their own obligation.
- (v) The government should cushion schools on procurement contracts for such components as transport, storage, and food preparation constitute another area where close monitoring and oversight are required, linked with strong tendering processes and transparency.

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